

HIERARCHICAL REGENERATED CELLULOSE FIBRE REINFORCED POLYHYDROXYBUTARATE

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1 General Introduction

High performance fibre reinforced polymer composites offer outstanding mechanical properties, high strength and stiffness yet lightweight. However, these materials are usually made with thermosetting matrices making their recyclability and reuse-ability difficult. Furthermore, most high performance fibres are manufactured from petrochemicals resources, which are not renewable [1,2]. Concurrently, much attention is paid to composites made from ‘greener’ alternatives such as natural fibres and biodegradable polymers. Natural and regenerated cellulosic fibres are becoming more common as they are available in abundance and are known for their advantages of coming from a natural source thus being fully renewable and biodegradable [3-7].

Although natural fibres are currently being used in the automotive industries, there are still a few disadvantages within this type of constituent. Natural fibres exist in random orientation, hence it is difficult to utilize the full parallel stiffness and strength of the fibres. Furthermore, natural fibres are susceptible to seasonal changes and therefore they are prone to have variation within the fibre quality. On the other hand, synthetic cellulose fibres, such as regenerated cellulose fibres, offers advantages to natural fibres on the uniform fibre quality and is available in a continuous form to be able to utilize the full

potential of cellulose chains. Furthermore, regenerated cellulose fibres are similar to natural fibres in having low fibre density and is of bio-based material [8]

In a conventional composite material, the overall strength, stiffness and toughness are not only governed by the mechanical characteristics of the reinforcing fibres but the ability of stress transfer between the two constituents. Therefore, a strong interface between the reinforcement and the surrounding matrix is vital in making composite material with reasonably high mechanical performance. There have been many studies made to improve the interface between natural/cellulosic fibres and conventional polymer matrices.

In this study, we focus on manufacturing truly-green hierarchical composites by incorporating continuous regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) fibres into poly-3-hydroxybutyrate containing 2.5 wt% nano-cellulose fibrils. Regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) fibre reinforced polymers have a decent elastic moduli (12-20 GPa), are light-weight and have a significant energy absorption capacity and, hence, great potential in the automotive sector [6]. Nano cellulose fibrils have were the matrix to improve the interfacial properties between natural fibres and surrounding polymer [9]. On the other hand, polyhydroxybutyrate is a biodegradable polymer [1], which is extremely brittle and has a

very low melt viscosity. Due to these attributes, it is almost impossible to process polyhydroxylbutyrate using conventional manufacturing processes, such as injection moulding or extrusion [10]. Nevertheless, polyhydroxylbutyrate is biodegradable and readily available in fine powder. The biggest challenge in working with this polymer as matrix for composites is choosing the correct processing routes to overcome the shortcomings of this polymer.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Continuous regenerated cellulose fibre (Cordenka[®] Rayon) rovings having 2440 tex size were kindly supplied by Cordenka GmbH & Co. KG (Oberburg, Germany). The matrix used was polyhydroxylbutyrate with $d_{50} = 34 \mu\text{m}$ was kindly supplied by BIOMER (Krailing, Germany). The nanocellulose fibrils were kindly supplied by United Paper Mills (Helsinki, Finland), Cremophor A25 was used as the surfactant to disperse and stabilize the polymer powder for wet impregnation and was supplied by BASF (Ludwigshafen, Germany). Ethanol (99.9% purity) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (UK).

2.2 Manufacturing of hierarchical unidirectional sustainable composites

The method used for manufacturing continuous hierarchical unidirectional regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) reinforced polyhydroxylbutyrate composites was wet-powder impregnation [9]. This method was chosen because it allows a good control when manufacturing unidirectional composites having a high fibre volume content. Regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) fibres were placed onto a tension let off unit with 100 g induced tension throughout the process. The fibres were then run through an impregnation

bath containing polyhydroxylbutyrate powder and nanocellulose fibrils in water. Surfactant was used to aid the dispersion of the powder. The bath was stirred throughout the production process to avoid powder sedimentation. The bath is also equipped with series of pins to further spread the fibres during the impregnation step. The impregnated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) fibres were then run through two-sets of infra-red heaters to remove the water and melt the polymer on the fibres. The manufacturing speed was set to 0.75 m/min. The fibre volume fraction was maintained to be $55 \pm 2 \%$. The resulting hierarchical unidirectional regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) fibre reinforced polyhydroxylbutyrate composite having a width of 12 mm and thickness of 0.1 mm were collected for mechanical characterisation. To determine the effect of addition of nanocellulose fibrils in the matrix, two control samples were also manufactured, i.e., unsized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®])- polyhydroxylbutyrate and sized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®])- polyhydroxylbutyrate.

2.3 Specimen preparation

The control specimens and hierarchical unidirectional regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) reinforced polyhydroxylbutyrate composites were cut into 200 mm long tape sections and were washed with ethanol to remove any contaminants coming from manufacturing and handling. The tapes were then stacked into a steel mould (200 mm x 12.5 mm). The mould was then placed into a hot press (Carver, USA) equipped with 4 platens (2 for heating and 2 for consolidation). The specimen were pressed at 1 tonne pressure and a temperature of 175 °C for 2 min after which it was placed in between the consolidation platens and further pressed at 0.5 tonne pressure and at temperature of 50 °C

for 10 min. the resulting composite laminate were then collected for further characterisation.

2.4 Axial tensile properties of unidirectional regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibres reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate

The tensile specimens were prepared according to ASTM D3039 [12] with a laminate dimension of 200 mm x 12.5 mm x 1.0 mm. Four strips of 50 mm long $\pm 45^\circ$ glass fibre reinforced epoxy composite tabs were used as end tabs leaving 100 mm gauge length on the test specimen. The surface of the end tabs and specimen to which the end tabs were glued were sand blasted to ensure a good adhesion between the two surfaces. The end tabs were then glued onto the test specimen by using CN Adhesive (General purpose, Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co. Ltd., Japan). A strain gauge, FLA 2-11 (Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co. Ltd., Japan) was placed in the centre of the gauge length of the specimen and glued using CN adhesive. Tensile tests were carried out at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min in an Instron 4505 (Instron, High Wycombe, Buckinghamshire, UK), equipped with 10 kN load cell. Every effort was made to correctly align the specimens in the jaws of the machine, thus ensuring a width-wise uniform stress field. The test was carried out until failure and the ultimate tensile strength σ_{tu} and tensile chord modulus of elasticity (Young's modulus E^{chord}) were calculated based on the following equations;

$$\sigma^{tu} = \frac{P_{MAX}}{A} \quad (1)$$

and

$$E^{chord} = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\varepsilon} \quad (2)$$

where P_{MAX} is the maximum load at failure (N), A is the average cross section area (mm^2), $\Delta\sigma$ and $\Delta\varepsilon$ are the difference in tensile stress and strain between strain points of 0.001 and 0.003, respectively. The test was carried out on 5 specimens to obtain statistical average values and the errors presented are standard deviations.

2.5 Flexural properties of unidirectional regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibres reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate

Flexural moduli and flexural strengths are of importance in engineering practice because composites are often subjected to bending load. This test was also performed to understand the effect of nanocellulose fibrils on the interface between regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibres and polyhydroxybutyrate as this test is also considered as an interface dominated test. Unidirectional regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibres reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate specimens with dimensions of 100 mm x 12.5 mm x 2 mm were prepared using compression moulding. The specimens were loaded into a three-point bending rig (with span-to-thickness ratio of 32:1) equipped with a 1 kN load cell (model 5581, Instron, Buckinghamshire, UK). The test was carried out according to the ASTM D790-03 standard [13] with a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min until failure. The flexural strength σ_f and flexural modulus E_f were calculated using the following equations:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3P_{MAX}S}{2bh^2} \left[1 + 6\left(\frac{D}{S}\right)^2 - 4\left(\frac{h}{S}\right)\left(\frac{D}{S}\right) \right] \quad (3)$$

and

$$E_f = \frac{S^3m}{4bh^3} \quad (4)$$

where D is the central deflection of the specimen at failure load P_{MAX} , S the span length,

m the gradient of the initial part of the force-displacement curve, b the specimen width and h the specimen thickness. The flexural strength and modulus of composite laminates were calculated from 5 measurements in order to obtain statistically relevant values.

3 Results and Discussion

Two types of Cordenka® rayon fibres (2440 dtex) were used in this work; sized and unsized. The fibres were first characterised using various methods to determine the strength of the reinforcement. It was found that the unsized fibres, having a smaller diameter possess a higher tensile strength and modulus as compared to sized fibres. Furthermore, the strain to failure of the unsized fibre was found to be 14% higher as compared to the sized fibre. To further understand the mechanical behavior of the composites, hierarchical unidirectional regenerated (Cordenka®) cellulose fibre reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate composites were subjected to both tension and flexural tests.

An example of the load vs. displacement curves of each individual composite specimens are shown in Figure 1-4. The tensile strength of unsized regenerated (Cordenka®) cellulose reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate was found to be 6% higher than that of sized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate composites. Furthermore, with incorporation of nanocellulose fibrils in the regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate matrix boost up the tensile strength of the composite furthermore. The tensile strength of both unsized and sized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibre reinforced regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate with 2.5 wt% of nanocellulose fibrils were found to be 16 and 15% respectively, as compared to the respective control composites without nanocellulose

fibrils. However, the Young's moduli of these composites were found to be about 15 GPa. The incorporation of nanocellulose fibrils or the use of either sized or unsized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibres does not seem to have any effect on the stiffness of the material. Similarly, the strain to failure of all the composite prepared were found to be 12% regardless of fibre sizing as well as addition of nanocellulose fibrils. This shows that the nanocellulose fibrils do help to strengthen the regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibres along the fibre direction, hence improving the tensile strength of the resulting composites.

Similarly, the flexural strength of unsized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibre reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate was found to be 18% higher than the composites made with sized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibres (Fig. 5). A more significant improvement in the flexural strength was found for the composites made with the incorporation of nanocellulose fibrils. An increase in the flexural strength of up to 15% and 33% was found for composites made with unsized and sized regenerated (Cordenka®) fibres, respectively as compared composites made without nanocellulose fibrils. This improvement shows that the incorporation of nanocellulose fibrils increased the strength of the composites possibly due to a stiffening of the matrix between the fibres through the matrix when load is applied on the composite. The nanocellulose fibrils incorporated forms a denser network on the regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibres hence the stiffening of the matrix, which allows for better support of the fibres. The flexural modulus on the other hand improves 6% and 30% for unsized and sized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) fibre reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate with 2.5 wt% of nanocellulose fibrils, respectively, as compared to the control composites.

4. Conclusions

The results of the study showed that these renewable green composites possess reasonable mechanical properties which could be used as alternative material to glass fibre composites for various non-load bearing applications. In addition, the flexibility of the manufacturing process of UD composites was demonstrated to allow for the production of high loading fraction regenerated cellulose composites using the notoriously difficult to process PHB as a matrix. The incorporation of nanocellulose fibrils in the composites showed significant improvement in the strength of the composite manufactured.

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Figure 1 Load vs. displacement of unidirectional unsized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate composites

Figure 2 Load vs. displacement of unidirectional sized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate composites

Figure 3 Load vs. displacement of unidirectional hierarchical unsized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka®) reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate composites

sized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) fibre reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate composite

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Figure 4 Load vs. displacement of unidirectional hierarchical sized regenerated cellulose (Cordenka[®]) reinforced polyhydroxybutyrate composites

Figure 5 Flexural strength and modulus of unidirectional and hierarchical unsize- and

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